

The Influence of Information System Usage, Work Motivation, and Work Discipline on Teacher Performance at SMP Negeri 7 Malang

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ABSTRACT

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Teacher performance is one of the important aspects that determine the quality of the learning process in schools. In practice, improving teacher performance often faces various obstacles related to the use of technology, motivation levels, and discipline in carrying out tasks. Common problems found in schools include delays in preparing learning administration, suboptimal use of technology-based media and information systems, and irregularities in performing daily tasks. These conditions indicate that the factors of information system use, work motivation, and work discipline are critical components that significantly influence teacher performance and need to be analyzed more deeply as part of efforts to improve education quality. This study aims to analyze the effect of these three variables on teacher performance. The approach used is quantitative with a questionnaire instrument distributed to teachers as respondents. The data were analyzed statistically to examine both partial and simultaneous effects among variables. The results of the study show that the use of the Si Spentu Information System has a positive and significant effect on teacher performance, followed by work motivation, which also significantly contributes to improving the effectiveness and quality of task implementation. Work discipline has been proven to be an important factor that positively affects teacher consistency and professionalism. Simultaneously, the use of the information system, work motivation, and work discipline have a positive and significant effect on teacher performance at SMP Negeri 7 Malang. These findings confirm that improving teacher performance requires the integrated strengthening of these three aspects.

KEYWORDS:

information systems, work motivation, work discipline, teacher performance

1. INTRODUCTION

Human resources (HR) are a key factor in achieving organizational goals, including in the field of education. Teachers, as educators, play a central role in determining the quality of learning in schools. According to Ginting et al., (2024), improving the quality of teacher HR is crucial in determining the quality of education because teachers are the main element in the learning process that is oriented towards achieving student learning outcomes. Improving teacher performance is a very important aspect in maintaining the quality of education at schools. However, teacher performance at SMP Negeri 7 Malang still shows several

issues that hinder the achievement of the professional standards expected by the school. Based on the initial interviews with the school and the review of administrative documents, it appears that some teachers have not been able to complete the preparation of teaching tools such as Teaching Modules and assessment reports on time. This situation reflects limitations in terms of ability, particularly related to the mastery of planning and managing learning administration. In addition, several teachers still make limited use of technology as a teaching medium and tend to stick to conventional methods. This indicates that motivation to innovate in the teaching process has not yet developed optimally. On the other hand, some teachers face challenges such as additional workload, limited supporting facilities, and working conditions that are not fully conducive, which reduces their opportunities to work effectively. As one of the important factors directly related to teacher performance, work discipline needs to be given primary attention. Work discipline is an aspect that significantly affects organizational effectiveness and individual responsibility at work. Marzuki

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(2022) stated that work discipline is closely related to academic supervision and has a significant impact on teachers' performance in schools. In line with this, Febriani et al. (2023) found that teachers with high levels of discipline tend to demonstrate better work productivity, punctual attendance, and the ability to conduct learning consistently and orderly. However, the ideal conditions have not yet been fully realized at SMP Negeri 7 Malang. Based on initial observations, issues with work discipline were found, such as arriving late, leaving before working hours end, and irregularities in completing learning administration. This situation reflects a lack of application of disciplinary principles, which impacts the effectiveness of learning activities and reduces the quality of educational services (Tatoo, 2020). The issue of discipline indicates that there are managerial aspects and supporting technologies that have not been functioning optimally within the school environment. In this context, the use of information systems becomes one of the factors that can help improve administrative effectiveness and monitor teacher performance. Along with the development of digital technology, school management information systems have become a vital instrument in modern educational administration. Research by Purnamawati et al. (2022) shows that the implementation of web-based educational management information systems can increase administrative efficiency, accelerate the reporting process, and facilitate school principals in decision-making. A similar point was made by Hamid (2025), who stated that an integrated school information system can assist in monitoring teacher attendance, assessments, and learning activities in real-time. However, the reality at SMP Negeri 7 Malang shows that the use of the "Si Spentu" information system by teachers has not been fully optimal. Some teachers are still adapting to operating the system's features, so several administrative processes and performance data management are still conducted semi-manually using Excel worksheets or physical documents as support. This situation occasionally causes delays in reporting learning administration and recording attendance, although, in general, the system has begun to be implemented. The principal still needs to provide guidance so that the use of "Si Spentu" can run more efficiently and be integrated according to the principles of technology-based administration, which emphasize speed, accuracy, and data integration in supporting educational decision-making. This condition is not yet in line with the principles of technology-based administration, which require speed, accuracy, and data integration to support the decision-making process in the field of education (Rumakat, 2025). In addition to issues of discipline and limited utilization of information technology, teachers' work motivation is also an important factor that influences their performance. Teachers with high motivation will demonstrate greater dedication, enthusiasm, and responsibility in carrying out their tasks. Astuti et al., (2020) found that work motivation directly

affects teacher discipline and performance and serves as a key driver in improving professionalism. Meanwhile, research by Zou et al., (2024) emphasizes that intrinsic motivation, such as recognition, rewards, and opportunities for growth, plays an important role in enhancing job satisfaction and teacher performance in secondary schools. Nevertheless, the field conditions at SMP Negeri 7 Malang indicate that teachers' work motivation has not yet reached an optimal level. Based on the results of the initial interviews, several teachers stated that they felt they received insufficient recognition for their achievements, as well as limited opportunities for self-development and taking on new responsibilities. In addition, the school's policies regarding the reward and punishment system were considered inconsistent and not transparent, while supervision by the principal had not been conducted intensively and continuously. This situation reflects weak motivational factors as described by Sipahutar et al., (2022), which impacts low work enthusiasm and a decline in overall teacher performance. When viewed more broadly, issues of work discipline, use of information systems, and work motivation are interconnected and collectively influence teachers' performance as the frontline of educational success. As explained by Hasibuan & Hadijaya (2024), organizational behavior and individual performance in educational institutions are influenced by the interaction between motivation, ability, and the work environment, supported by an effective managerial system. In other words, improving teachers' performance can only be achieved if factors such as motivation, discipline, and support from information systems work synergistically. Based on the conditions at SMP Negeri 7 Malang, it can be concluded that the issues with teacher performance are closely related to three main factors, namely the use of information systems, work motivation, and work discipline. Therefore, this study was conducted under the title "The Influence of the Use of Information Systems, Work Motivation, and Work Discipline on Teacher Performance at SMP Negeri 7 Malang." This research is expected to provide an empirical overview of the relationship among these three factors and serve as input for the school in improving the quality of education through the continuous enhancement of teacher performance.

III. RESULTS

A. The Influence of Information System Use on Teacher Performance

Based on research findings, the use of information systems plays a clear role in improving teacher performance at SMP Negeri 7 Malang. The more optimally teachers utilize information systems in their daily activities, the better the quality of performance they demonstrate in carrying out professional duties. The use of information systems supports the effectiveness of teachers' work in various aspects, ranging from lesson planning, classroom administration management, to the implementation of learning outcome evaluations. This

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system helps teachers complete tasks more quickly, accurately, and in an organized manner. In the school environment, information systems are commonly used to manage academic data, student attendance, assessments, as well as the reporting of learning outcomes in a more structured and easily accessible way.

B. The Influence of Work Motivation on Teacher Performance

Based on research findings, work motivation plays a strong role in shaping and improving teacher performance at SMP Negeri 7 Malang. Teachers who have high drive and willingness to work generally demonstrate better performance quality compared to teachers with low motivation. These findings indicate that work motivation is one of the important factors that determine how teachers carry out their professional functions on a daily basis. Good work motivation makes teachers more enthusiastic in planning and implementing learning activities. They tend to show initiative in developing varied teaching methods, adapting teaching materials to student needs, and striving to create an engaging and meaningful learning environment. This dedication is reflected in how teachers prepare teaching materials, their diligence in providing feedback to students, and consistency in applying objective and continuous assessment.

C. The Influence of Work Discipline on Teacher Performance

Based on research findings, work discipline has been proven to play an important role in improving the performance of teachers at SMP Negeri 7 Malang. The higher the level of discipline demonstrated by teachers, the better the quality of work they produce in carrying out their professional duties. These findings confirm that work discipline is one of the main indicators that determine a teacher's effectiveness in fulfilling their roles and responsibilities at school.

D. The Influence of Information System Usage, Work Motivation, and Work Discipline on Teacher Performance

Based on the research findings, the use of information systems, work motivation, and work discipline has been proven to have a strong influence when combined together in improving the performance of teachers at SMP Negeri 7 Malang. These three variables complement each other and provide a direct contribution to the quality of teachers' professional task implementation.

IV. DISCUSSION

A. The Influence of Information System Use on Teacher Performance Based on research findings, the use of information systems plays a clear role in improving teacher performance at SMP Negeri 7 Malang. The more optimally teachers utilize information systems in their daily activities, the better the quality of performance they demonstrate in carrying out professional duties. The use

of information systems supports the effectiveness of teachers' work in various aspects, ranging from lesson planning, classroom administration management, to the implementation of learning outcome evaluations. This system helps teachers complete tasks more quickly, accurately, and in an organized manner. In the school environment, information systems are commonly used to manage academic data, student attendance, assessments, as well as the reporting of learning outcomes in a more structured and easily accessible way.

In addition, the use of information systems facilitates communication between teachers, principals, and education staff. A more open and integrated flow of information aids the coordination process, allowing decisions to be made more accurately and responsively. Teachers who are accustomed to operating information systems demonstrate more optimal performance because all work processes are supported by efficient, transparent, and accountability-enhancing digital systems. These results are in line with the research of Nurhidayanti (2025), which shows that the implementation of a school management information system significantly affects teacher performance because it helps save time and reduces errors in administrative work. Research by Zulfa & Arifudin (2025) also supports this finding, stating that the use of an academic information system increases teacher productivity and facilitates the assessment and reporting process. In addition, research by Furmaisuri et al. (2025) shows that teachers who actively use digital information systems have higher performance compared to those who still use conventional methods. The use of information systems makes it easier for teachers to access learning data and adjust teaching strategies based on student needs. The results of this study are in line with the Technology Acceptance Model (Davis, 1989), which states that the usefulness and ease of use of technology influence an individual's acceptance of that technology. Teachers who understand the benefits of information systems and find them easy to use will be encouraged to utilize them consistently, thereby impacting performance improvement. In addition, the Educational Information Management theory from (Laudon & Laudon, 2018) asserts that information systems play a role in collecting, processing, storing, and distributing information to support decision-making and coordination in the school environment. In this context, information systems help teachers make accurate and efficient decisions in both the learning process and administration. Thus, it can be concluded that the use of information systems is an important factor in improving teacher performance at SMP Negeri 7 Malang. Teachers who are able to adapt to technological developments and make optimal use of information systems will demonstrate more effective, efficient, and professional performance in carrying out their duties.

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B. The Influence of Work Motivation on Teacher Performance

Based on research findings, work motivation plays a strong role in shaping and improving teacher performance at SMP Negeri 7 Malang. Teachers who have high drive and willingness to work generally demonstrate better performance quality compared to teachers with low motivation. These findings indicate that work motivation is one of the important factors that determine how teachers carry out their professional functions on a daily basis. Good work motivation makes teachers more enthusiastic in planning and implementing learning activities. They tend to show initiative in developing varied teaching methods, adapting teaching materials to student needs, and striving to create an engaging and meaningful learning environment. This dedication is reflected in how teachers prepare teaching materials, their diligence in providing feedback to students, and consistency in applying objective and continuous assessment. In addition, teachers with high motivation usually demonstrate a sense of responsibility and loyalty towards the tasks that are their duties. They are more disciplined in completing learning administration, punctual in managing assessments, and actively maintain communication with parents and colleagues. Such commitment makes an important contribution to improving the quality of educational services at schools. The results of this study are consistent with the findings of Anggraeni (2021), who stated that motivation, both intrinsic and extrinsic, has a significant impact on teacher performance in schools. Teachers who receive recognition and support from leadership will demonstrate higher performance in the teaching and learning process. Likewise, the study by Mustika & Syamsuddin (2022) emphasizes that work motivation is a dominant factor in determining teacher performance, as it is directly related to job satisfaction and commitment. In addition, this finding is also reinforced by Gusli (2024), who found that teachers with high motivation are more proactive in developing themselves, participating in training, and innovating in learning strategies, which ultimately impacts the improvement of performance quality. Theoretically, the results of this study are in line with Herzberg's Two-Factor Theory (1959), which emphasizes that an individual's motivation and performance are influenced by motivator factors such as achievement, responsibility, and recognition of work results. These factors encourage individuals to work more enthusiastically and productively because they feel their work is meaningful and provides intrinsic satisfaction. Therefore, it can be concluded that work motivation has a significant impact on improving teacher performance at SMP Negeri 7 Malang. Teachers with high motivation not only demonstrate discipline and responsibility but also innovate in teaching, are results-oriented, and are committed to the progress of the school. Consequently, school management needs to strengthen performance-based reward systems, provide opportunities for

professional development, and create a positive and supportive work environment. These steps will strengthen teachers' work motivation so that overall performance at SMP Negeri 7 Malang can continue to improve and contribute to better quality education.

C. The Influence of Work Discipline on Teacher Performance

Based on research findings, work discipline has been proven to play an important role in improving the performance of teachers at SMP Negeri 7 Malang. The higher the level of discipline demonstrated by teachers, the better the quality of work they produce in carrying out their professional duties. These findings confirm that work discipline is one of the main indicators that determine a teacher's effectiveness in fulfilling their roles and responsibilities at school. Work discipline reflects the extent to which a teacher can adhere to rules, use time efficiently, and maintain consistency in carrying out tasks. A disciplined teacher demonstrates readiness in teaching, arrives on time, and prepares learning materials before entering the classroom. This disciplined attitude makes the learning process more organized and has a positive impact on achieving educational goals. At SMP Negeri 7 Malang, observation results show that teachers with high discipline consistently provide evaluations of learning outcomes, complete class administration, and participate in school activities according to schedule. Moreover, work discipline is not only related to physical attendance but also includes aspects of moral responsibility, work ethics, and professional commitment. Disciplined teachers will maintain integrity in carrying out their duties, adhere to professional codes of ethics, and serve as role models for students. They tend to work in an organized, neat, and procedural manner, ensuring that both teaching activities and administrative tasks run effectively. At SMP Negeri 7 Malang, the implementation of a digital attendance system, app-based administrative reporting, and performance monitoring by the principal also strengthen the culture of discipline in the workplace. These measures encourage teachers to be more responsible and consistent in carrying out their duties. In addition, a collaborative work culture, open communication, and ongoing academic supervision help create a productive and professional working environment. The combination of these factors makes work discipline one of the key determinants of overall teacher performance improvement. The results of this study support the findings of Sunarko et al. (2022), which indicate that work discipline has a positive and significant effect on teacher performance in the Tamansiswa Foundation branch schools in Malang. Teachers with a high level of discipline demonstrate better productivity and responsibility in managing learning activities. Research by Pratiwi et al. (2025) also found that work discipline is a determining factor in a teacher's success in achieving performance targets, as discipline reflects consistency and

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loyalty to the profession. Furthermore, the study by et al. (2025) confirmed that teachers with a high level of discipline adapt more easily to changes in school policies and are more focused on carrying out their main tasks. From a theoretical perspective, this result is in line with the Discipline Theory according to Rivai (2018), which states that discipline is a reflection of a person's compliance, awareness, and responsibility toward the regulations and values applicable within an organization. Discipline is not only understood as adherence to written rules but also includes a moral commitment to work in an orderly, timely, and professional manner. Individuals with a high level of discipline usually demonstrate strong integrity and a sense of responsibility toward their work, enabling them to maintain consistent performance and contribute positively to achieving organizational goals. In the context of education, disciplined teachers serve as role models for students, adhere to school rules, conduct lessons according to schedules, and maintain the quality of the teaching and learning process. Thus, discipline, as explained by Rivai, becomes an important foundation for creating a productive work culture oriented towards quality. Thus, it can be concluded that work discipline has a significant influence on the performance of teachers at SMP Negeri 7 Malang. Discipline serves as the main foundation in shaping the professional character of teachers who are responsible, have integrity, and are oriented towards achieving optimal work results. Therefore, the school needs to continuously foster a culture of discipline through a reward system for high-achieving teachers, fair supervision, and the consistent implementation of work rules. These efforts are believed to be able to promote sustainable teacher performance improvement and strengthen the quality of education at SMP Negeri 7 Malang.

D. The Influence of Information System Usage, Work Motivation, and Work Discipline on Teacher Performance

Based on the research findings, the use of information systems, work motivation, and work discipline has been proven to have a strong influence when combined together in improving the performance of teachers at SMP Negeri 7 Malang. These three variables complement each other and provide a direct contribution to the quality of teachers' professional task implementation. The use of information systems serves as a primary support in carrying out administrative tasks as well as learning activities. At SMP Negeri 7 Malang, the information system used is Si Spentu, which functions as a digital platform to integrate various school needs such as assessments, attendance, class schedules, learning reports, and class administration. This system helps teachers manage their work more structurally, speeds up the data entry process, and ensures the accuracy of the information needed in the educational process. The use of Si Spentu makes it easier for teachers to prepare reports,

access students' academic data, and carry out administrative tasks more efficiently. Work motivation also enhances the benefits of using this information system. Teachers with high motivation will maximize the use of technology, be more creative in designing learning, and show strong commitment in carrying out educational tasks. This motivational drive makes teachers more responsive to changes, willing to attend professional training, and continuously develop their skills. Work motivation becomes a driving force that enables teachers to perform optimally, both in pedagogical and managerial aspects. Work discipline also makes a significant contribution to improving teacher performance. Teachers with high discipline will use their time effectively, adhere to applicable rules, and complete tasks on time. Discipline is reflected in the teacher's presence in class according to schedule, readiness of teaching materials, accuracy in managing assessments, and consistency in participating in school activities. At SMP Negeri 7 Malang, the implementation of digital attendance through Si Spentu and regular supervision by the principal encourages the formation of a more orderly and directed work pattern. When the use of information systems, work motivation, and work discipline occur simultaneously, a professional and productive work environment is created. The utilization of Si Spentu increases the efficiency and accountability of teachers' tasks, work motivation provides the drive to innovate and develop, while work discipline ensures that all educational processes run according to established procedures and schedules. The combination of these three factors fosters an effective and sustainable work culture, which ultimately has a positive impact on improving the quality of learning at SMP Negeri 7 Malang. These findings are consistent with the results of previous research. Saputra et al. (2024) found that research results indicate that the principal's leadership style and work motivation affect teacher performance. The influence of leadership style on teacher performance is 53.9%. Furthermore, Simanjorang et al. (2025) stated that the implementation of an information system improves administrative efficiency, accelerates the processing of academic data, and facilitates real-time information access. This system also increases user satisfaction and supports transparency and the effectiveness of academic management at SMK 1 Delimasari Tiga Juhar. Gunawan et al., (2025) also concluded that work motivation, both intrinsic and extrinsic, along with work discipline, plays an important role in enhancing teachers' professionalism and performance. The synergy between motivation and discipline results in optimal performance, while an imbalance between the two lowers work quality. Therefore, school management needs to foster motivation and a culture of discipline to improve the quality of education. Theoretically, teacher performance can be explained through Campbell's Performance Theory (1990), which states that performance is the result of the interaction between ability, motivation, and work environment. In this

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context, the use of Si Spentu supports the work environment aspect by providing a system that facilitates task execution; work motivation acts as an internal driver that fosters the desire to achieve the best results; while work discipline serves as a behavioral control factor to ensure that teachers consistently work according to standards. These three aspects interact synergistically and produce optimal performance. Thus, it can be concluded that the use of the Si Spentu information system, work motivation, and work discipline simultaneously have a positive and significant impact on teacher performance at SMP Negeri 7 Malang. These three factors are the main pillars in enhancing teacher professionalism and productivity. Therefore, the school needs to continuously optimize the use of Si Spentu, provide motivational support through training and rewards, and enforce discipline so that teacher performance can improve sustainably and support the achievement of quality educational goals.

V. CONCLUSION

Based on the results of research and data analysis conducted regarding the influence of the use of the Si Spentu information system, work motivation, and work discipline on teacher performance, it can be concluded as follows:

1. The use of the Si Spentu Information System has a positive and significant effect on teacher performance. This shows that the more optimal the use of Si Spentu in administrative activities, reporting, and teacher performance assessments, the more the effectiveness of teachers' work increases. This system helps teachers with time efficiency, data accuracy, and work process transparency, which ultimately impacts the improvement of productivity and professional responsibility.
2. Work motivation has a positive and significant effect on teacher performance. Teachers who have high motivation, both intrinsic and extrinsic, tend to be more disciplined, creative, and focused on achieving the best results. A strong work ethic drives teachers to improve their competence and provide optimal educational services to students.
3. Work discipline has a positive and significant effect on teacher performance. Improvement in discipline is reflected in punctual attendance, adherence to school rules, and consistent completion of tasks. Good work discipline plays an important role in maintaining teachers' stability and professionalism in carrying out their duties.
4. The use of the Si Spentu Information System, work motivation, and work discipline simultaneously have a positive and significant effect on teacher performance. These three factors complement each other in creating a productive work environment. Spentu facilitates work efficiency, motivation acts as an internal driver, while discipline serves as an external controller that maintains consistency in teachers' work behavior. Thus, the

combination of the three results in optimal performance improvement.

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